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Research Paper

Formulation and Evaluation of Herbal Face Scrub Using Pomegranate Peel

Sakshi Tayade*¹, Vaishnavi Gawande¹, Sunil Bhagat², Swati Deshmukh³

¹Student of Bachelor of Pharmacy, Shraddha Institute of Pharmacy, Kondala Zambre, Washim-444 505

²Assistant Professor, Shraddha Institute of Pharmacy, Washim- 444 505.

³Professors, Department of Pharmacology, Shraddha Institute of Pharmacy, Kondala Zambre, Washim-444505

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ABSTRACT

In today's life for both women and men cosmetics plays an important role to beautifying and altering the appearance of skin. A facial scrub is a cosmetic or a beauty product used to exfoliate and clean the skin on the face and body. It helps remove dead skin cells, promote blood circulation, and rejuvenate the skin. The aim of study is to formulate and evaluate a face scrub with incorporation of the pomegranate as an active ingredient. Pomegranate was selected due to its natural antioxidant and skin-rejuvenating properties. The main objective of research study was to formulate an herbal scrub using natural ingredients incorporated into gel. Natural ingredients are preferred in herbal cosmetics due to their potential benefits in addressing skin issues such as acne, wrinkles, and excess oil production. The other ingredients like carbopol 940, triethanolamine, glycerine were added into this face scrub gel. The prepared face scrub were evaluated for various parameters such as organoleptic properties, pH, irritability, washability, grittiness, foamability, spreadability and found to be satisfactory outcome. The prepared formulation works well as a scrub that encourages healthy and radiant skin.

INTRODUCTION

Cosmetics are defined as the products used for the purpose of beautifying, cleansing, promoting attractiveness or alternating the appearance. From the ancient time, different herbs are used for cleaning, beautifying and to manage them. [1]

Face skin is the major part of the body, which indicates the health of an individual. Cosmetics are widely used to improve one's appearance and are available in a variety of forms. Skincare Products are formulated to address various skin issues, such as skin protection, sun protection, anti-aging, and anti-wrinkle treatments. Since ancient times,

*Corresponding Author: Sakshi Tayade

Address: Student of Bachelor of Pharmacy, Shraddha Institute of Pharmacy, Kondala Zambre, Washim-444 505

Email ✉: vishalrasve@gmail.com

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people have used herbs or herbal cosmetics to cleanse, beautify, and combat oil, acne, discoloration, and pimples, as well as dark circles. [2] Cosmetics are available as various forms and each has its own role to play on the skin. Skin becomes dull, non-glowing due to various causes and these can effectively be overcome with the application of scrubs. [3] Herbal cosmetics are in high demand nowadays. The name itself indicates that herbal cosmetics are natural and they do not contain any chemicals. Facial scrubs are an essential part of a skin care routine. A facial scrub is usually a cream-based product that contains little exfoliation pieces that when massaged across the skin help smooth the skin by physically lifting off dry, dead skin cells. A facial scrub is a cosmetic or a beauty product used to exfoliate and clean the skin on the face and body. Blackheads, whiteheads, sebum, and skin cells can all be removed by using face scrubs. [4] A face scrub is an effective way to cleanse the skin, remove dirt, grime, and oil from the pores, maintain elasticity, and promote the regeneration of skin cells. It exfoliates the skin and stimulates blood circulation, while also eliminating dead skin cells. The ideal properties of face scrubs are mild abrasive and non-aggressive. [5] Herbal exfoliating scrub helps to reduce the effects of age-related changes on the skin and neutralizes the damage caused by the environment. It can be used to technically clean the surface of the skin or to remove dead skin cells by using herbal products with anti-aging, vitamin, antioxidant, and antiseptic properties. This helps to deeply cleanse the skin, making it glow and attractive, and removes the dead skin cells. [6] In this face scrub, pomegranate is used as an active ingredient. The other ingredients like carbopol 940, triethanolamine, were added into this face scrub gel. The prepared face scrub was evaluated for various parameters such as organoleptic properties, pH, irritability, washability, grittiness,

foamability, spreadability and found to be a satisfactory outcome. The prepared formulation works well as a scrub that encourages healthy and radiant skin. The skin, being the largest organ in the human body, envelops the entire external surface, providing protection against a multitude of factors. With a surface area ranging from 1.5 to 2m², the skin functions as the body's primary defense mechanism against pathogens, Ultraviolet(UV) light, chemical substances and physical trauma. Moreover, it plays a crucial role in regulating body temperature and controlling the release of water into the surrounding environment.[7,8] The majority of dead skin cells on the surface of the skin on the face stay there for a longer period of time, which tends to highlight fine wrinkles and can give the complexion a lifeless, dull appearance. Dry skin, wrinkles, and dark spots are the second most common skin problems nowadays, behind acne and pimples. [9] Scrubbing is utilized to treat every skin condition, regardless of the type of skin. The skin's surface needs to be cleaned frequently in order to remove grime, sebum, and other secretions, dead cells, crusts, and makeup that has been applied in order to stay healthy and attractive. [10,11] Oily skin, sensitive skin, and dry skin are the three different types of skin. Use the face scrub, which has hydrating and moisturising components, if you have dry skin. A gentle scrub should be used if the person has sensitive skin. And the individual with oily skin should use an exfoliation that helps to manage oiliness while preventing breakouts, dullness, and pimples. [12] Face scrubs should be used twice or three times a week, depending on the kind of skin. But it's advised to use face washes once a week for beginners. Only one or two times per week should those with dry or sensitive skin exfoliate. Salicylic acid and dermatologist-grade 4% glycolic and polyhydroxy acid complex products are sometimes advised for usage by those with acne-prone skin. This gives skin a smoother

appearance while helping to exfoliate the skin and eliminate acne. [13]

Skin: Skin is the largest organ in the body and covers the body's entire external surface. It is

made up of three layers, the epidermis, dermis, and the hypodermis, all three of which vary significantly in their anatomy and function. The skin also regulates body temperature stores water and fats. [14,15]

Fig 1. Structure of skin

The skin is made up of 3 layers. Each layer has certain functions:

1. Epidermis
2. Dermis
3. Subcutaneous fat layer (hypodermis)

Epidermis:

The epidermis is the thin outer layer of the skin. It consists of 3 types of cells: Squamous cells. The

outermost layer is continuously shed is called the stratum corneum. Basal cells. Basal cells are found just under the squamous cells, at the base of the epidermis. Melanocytes. Melanocytes are also found at the base of the epidermis and make melanin this gives the skin its color.

Dermis:

The dermis is the middle layer of the skin. The dermis contains the following:

Fig 2. Dermis

The dermis is held together by a protein called collagen. This layer gives skin flexibility and strength. The dermis also contains pain and touch receptors.

Subcutaneous layer:

The subcutaneous fat layer is the deepest layer of skin. It consists of a network of collagen and fat cells. It helps conserve the body's heat and protects the body from injury by acting as a shock absorber. [16,17]

Face Scrub

A face scrub is a skincare product used to exfoliate your skin. It helps in the removal of dead skin cells from the surface of your skin, reducing the chances for clogged pores and acne breakouts. Facial scrubs contain coarse particles which help to exfoliate the skin. When you apply a face scrub,

the particles rub against your skin and remove all the dirt from your skin pores. It also removes dead skin cells, making your skin smoother and softer. The addition of a good facial scrub In your weekly skincare routine will provide you with healthy and glowing skin. [18] Facial scrub is a cosmetic or beauty product, or a treatment designed to cleanse and exfoliate the skin of the face or body. When using the scrub gel, a gentle massage is recommended to aid enhance blood circulation. [19]

Idea properties of face scrub

1. It should be Non- sticky and mild abrasive.
2. It should be Non-toxic.
3. It must removes dirt and dead skin.
4. It should Non-irritant.
5. It must contain small gritty particles. [20]

Steps to Use A Face Scrub

Step 1: Rinse your face with water thoroughly. Do not pat it dry.

Step 2: Take a nickel – sized amount of facial scrub in your palm.

Step 3: Apply the facial scrub on your wet face.

Step 4: Gently rub the scrub on your face, applying the least amount of pressure. You can rub the Scrub in a circular motion using your fingers.

Step 5: Always massage your face upwards and focus on areas like the top and corner of your nose, Cheeks and upper lips.

Step 6: Continue the massage for 10 to 15 seconds.

Step 7: Now move to your neck and under the chin and massage for another 10 seconds.

Step 8: Once you finish exfoliating, wash your face with cold or lukewarm water. [21]

Exfoliant

A facial scrub uses small particles, beads or chemicals to get rid of the old skin cells and make way for new once in a process known as exfoliation. The agents are used for exfoliation are known as exfoliants. Exfoliating agents are those used to remove dead cells present on the skin and boost blood circulation, giving renewed and glowing skin. It keeps face free from dust, grime and oils which are also beneficial in keeping a skin pore clean. There are two ways to exfoliate the skin. [22,23]

Selection of scrub based on skin type

➤ **For oily skin:** When their skin pores are clogged by additional sebum oil, people with oily skin typically struggle with acne issues. Therefore, requires a face scrub that not only gets rid of the skin's dead cells but also has

anti-pimple capabilities. The Anti-acne properties of salicylic acid are well established.

- **For dry skin:** Any face cleanser with components designed to remove dead skin cells can be used by those with dry skin. One Such chemical that eliminates flaky skin and dead skin cells quickly is glycolic acid. It is a well-known excellent exfoliant.
- **For sensitive skin:** While choosing skincare products, people with sensitive skin should be more cautious. A face scrub that is both antibacterial and anti-inflammatory is best if one have sensitive skin. Sugar scrubs are thought to be excellent for sensitive skin.
- **For combination skin:** Choosing a face scrub might be challenging because combination skin is a mix of dry and oily skin. however, according to specialists, persons with combination skin should use a facial scrub to remove extra oil from the skin without drying it out. [24]

Merits of scrub

- 1) To maintain pristine skin: To expose clean skin, scrub away dirt, sweat to reveal clean skin. Unfortunately, the containers of cleaning milk, face wash, and facial cleansers can't get rid of all the dust that builds up in your skin's pores. This is effectively accomplished via scrubbing.
- 2) Eliminates skin flakes: Patches of dry skin result from flaky skin. It permits the accumulation of dead cells over time. One can easily treat flaky skin by exfoliating it.
- 3) Improving skin's texture: Skin will be cleaner, smoother, and have a better texture after a good scrub. [25]

Demerits of scrub

- 1) Skin irritation, including redness and inflammation, can be brought on by harsh rubbing movements and chemicals. A person with sensitive skin may potentially experience allergic responses to the chemicals found in synthetic scrubs.
- 2) Over scrubbing can leave pores open, exposing the skin to both UV radiation and pollution. A skin may become more vulnerable to infections and tanning as a result. [26]

Plant Profile

Pomegranate

Synonyms: Anar, Dalim

Botanical Name: Punica granatum

Biological source: The pomegranate (*Punica granatum*) is a fruit-bearing deciduous shrub

Family: Lythraceae

Chemical constituents: Punicalagin, Punicalin, Gallic acid, Ellagic acid, Punicalagin A

Punicalagin B, Ellagic acid, Gallic acid, ellagitannins

Uses:

- 1) Pomegranate peel powder can be used as a natural exfoliant to remove dead skin cells.
- 2) It helps hydrating and nourishing to the skin.
- 3) It also improves skin elasticity, enhance skin tone.
- 4) It shows Antioxidant Properties, Protects against sun damage.
- 5) It Reduces fine lines and wrinkles, Fades age spots.
- 6) Gentle Exfoliation: Pomegranate peel powder is a gentle exfoliant that helps remove dead skin cells without irritating the skin.
- 7) Antioxidant Properties: Pomegranate peel powder contains antioxidants that help protect the skin from environmental stressors and promote healthy skin cell growth.
- 8) Improved Skin Texture: Regular use of pomegranate peel powder can help improve skin texture, leaving skin feeling smooth and soft. [27]

Fig 3. Pomegranate

Tumeric

Synonym: Haldi, Haridra, Curcumin.

Biological source: Turmeric consist of dried as well as fresh rhizomes of the

Plant *Curcuma longa*

Family: Zingiberaceae.

Description:

Colour- Brilliant yellow.

Odour- mildly aromatic.

Taste- Pleasantly bitter and earthy.

Chief chemical constituents: Non-volatile curcuminoids and the volatile oil; Curcuminoids contains curcumin, demethoxycurcumin, bisdemethoxycurcumin.

Uses:

1. It is used as Anti-septic; traditionally used for disorders of skin; anti-inflammatory; fights free radical damages.
2. Anti-inflammatory properties decrease the skin's inflammation; and speed up the skin's ability to form new tissue.
3. Besides the fact that turmeric is naturally gold, it can help bring out your natural glow. By reducing dark spots and hyperpigmentation, your skin looks naturally even and radiant. [28]

Fig 4. Turmeric

Neem

Synonym – Neem

Biological source – It consists of dried leaves of *Azadirachta indica*

Family: Meliaceae.

Description:

Colour Green

Odour – Pungent

Taste – Bitter

Chief chemical constituents Nimbinin, Nimbidin, Quercetin

Uses:

1. It is used antifungal, antibacterial, antiseptic and anti-inflammatory, lightens scars, and tackles whiteheads and blackheads.
2. Vitamin C is abundant in neem, which aids in the natural creation of collagen and infuses the skin with antioxidants to reduce fine wrinkles.
3. Neem is often used as a toner to cleanse your skin when using it for acne. Neem's antimicrobial qualities remove excess oil from the skin pores.
4. Neem products are often recommended with skincare and beautification routines to address dry skin and wrinkles.
5. The antioxidants reduce the formation of melanin in your skin, which helps to cure your skin tone. It also helps to minimise your dark spots, dry skin and redness on the skin. [29]

Fig 5. Neem

Honey

Synonym: Shahad, Madhu, Madh, Madhvikā.

Biological source: Honey is sugary substance deposited in the honeycomb by the bee

Apis mellifera

Family- Apidae.

Description:

Colour- Pale Yellow to reddish brown.

Odour- Pleasant and characteristic.

Taste- Sweet

Chief chemical constituent: Glucose, fructose, sucrose, dextrin, formic acid, succinic Acid, gums.

Uses:

1. It is used demulcent, antiseptic, antioxidant, vehicle for ayurvedic formulation, anti-Inflammatory, topically to treat burns, sweetening agent and promote wound healing.
2. A skin condition that causes redness on the face. Applying a topical honey product to the skin might improve symptoms of rosacea.
3. Honey seems to reduce odours and pus, help clean the wound, reduce infection, reduce pain, and decrease time to healing and also used as humectant. [30]

Fig 6. Honey

Aloe vera

Synonym: Aloe; Ghritakumari.

Biological source: Dried juice collected from incision from the bases of the leaves of

Vitamins, enzymes, minerals, sugars, lignin, saponins, salicylic acids and amino acids.

Aloe Barbadensis or *aloe officinalis*

Uses:

Family: Liliaceae.

Description:

Colour- The leaves are grey to green.

Odour- Penetrating odour.

Taste- Nauseous and bitter.

1. It moisturize skin, treat various skin conditions, including acne, eczema, and sunburn, Anti-cancer, anti- oxidant, anti-diabetic first- and second-degree sunburns have both been successfully treated with it.
2. It has been discovered that aloe vera gel shields human skin from all negative effects of radiation. [31]

Chief chemical constituent- Aloe-emodin is main constituent. It also contains

Fig 7. Aloe Vera

Rose water

Colour: light pinky-blush

Synonym: Attar of rose, lavender water, scented liquid.

Odour- Aromatic

Biological source: Rose water is obtained from sepals and petals of *Rosa damascena* through steam distillation.

Chief chemical constituent- The volatiles mainly consist of 2- phenylehanol, linalool, Citronellol, nerol, geraniol, etc.

Family- Rosaceae.

Uses:

Description:

1. It smoothens skin irritation, reduce skin redness, heals cuts and scars, treat burns. [32]

Fig 8. Rose water

Excipients profile:

- **Glycerin**

1) **Synonym-** Sugar alcohol, polyol, glycerol.

2) **IUPAC name-** Propane-1, 2, 3-triol.

3) **Molecular formula-** C₃H₈O₃.

4) **Molecular weight-** 92.09382 g/ mol.

5) **Uses-**

1. It is known to serve various functions in cosmetics, such as denaturation, fragrance enhancement, hair conditioning, moisture retention, oral care support, skin protection, and viscosity modulation.
2. The skincare benefits of using rose water include hydration, nourishment, calming irritation and redness, reducing dark circles and puffiness under the eyes, controlling excess oil, minimizing pores, and reducing the appearance of fine lines and wrinkles. [29]

- **Carbopol**

1) **Chemical Name-** Carbomer

2) **IUPAC name-** Poly (acrylic acid), poly (1-carboxyethylene)

3) **Molecular formula-**(C₃H₄O₂)_n

4) **Molecular weight-**713.1 g/mol

5) **Functional category-** Bioadhesive material, controlled-release agent, emulsifying agent, emulsion stabilizer, rheology modifier, stabilizing agent, suspending agent, tablet binder.

6) **Synonym-** Acrypol, Acritamer, acrylic acid polymer, carbomera, Carbopol, carboxy Polymethylene, polyacrylic acid, carboxyvinyl polymer, Pemulen, Tego Carbomer.

7) **Uses-**

1. Carbopol is used as a thickener in lotions, creams and gels.
2. It is also used to stabilize, suspend, and control the release of pharmaceutical products.

- **Triethanolamie**

1) **IUPAC name-** N, N-diethylethanamine

2) **Molecular formula-** C₆H₁₅NO₃

3) **Molecular weight-** 149.19 g/mol petroleum demulsifiers, toilet goods, cement additives, and cutting oils. [33]

4) **Functional category-** Alkalizing agent, emulsifying agent.

5) **Synonyms-** Tealan, triethylamine, trihydroxy triethylamine, tris (hydroxyethyl) amine, Trolamine.

6) **Uses:**

1. Triethanolamine is used as an intermediate in the manufacturing of surfactants, textile specialties, waxes, polishes, herbicides,

MATERIAL AND METHOD:

Collection of material

Pomegranate peel collected from market. Neem leaves and aloe vera were collected from garden. Honey, tumeric powder are collected from market. Carbopol 940, triethanolamine, glycerine, rosewater were procured from laboratory of Shradha Institute of Pharmacy, Washim

Table No.1: Formulation table of face scrub

Sr. No	Ingredient	F1	F2	F3	Uses
1	Pomegranate peel powder	3 g	2.5 g	2 g	Exfoliant
2	Tumeric powder	1 g	1 g	1 g	Glowing skin, moisturizing dry skin
3	Neem powder	2 g	2.5 g	3 g	Antiseptic, improve fairness
4	Aloe vera gel	5 ml	5 ml	5 ml	Moisturizer
5	Honey	5 ml	4 ml	3 ml	Antioxidant, antiseptic
6	Glycerine	3 ml	3 ml	3 ml	Emollient
7	Carbopol 940	0.3 g	0.3 g	0.3 g	Gelling agent
8	Triethanolamine	0.2 ml	0.2 ml	0.2 ml	Neutralizer
9	Rose water	Q.S	Q. S	Q. S	Vehicle
Total		30 gm	30 gm	30gm	

METHODOLOGY

1. Washing

Rinse raw materials under running water to remove dirt or impurities.

2. Drying

All drugs were dried under shade to remove the moisture.

3. Powdering of drugs

- All ingredients were taken in equal quantity.
- Before powdering each sample, the mortar, pestle and grinder were properly cleaned.

- All ingredients were pounded in mortar and pestle before grinding.
- All ingredients were powdered in a mixer-grinder and sieved through, use a 80–100 mesh sieve to get uniform, fine powder suitable for scrub.
- The grinding and sieving was repeatedly done up to complete sieving of powder
- Ingredients.
- Finally, the finished was packed in the sterilized closed container.

4. Mixing of ll ingredients

➤ Phase A: Gel Base Preparation

Step 1: Weighing of Ingredients

Accurately weigh all ingredients according to the formulation table

Step 2: Carbopol Dispersion

Slowly sprinkle 0.3g of Carbopol 940 into measured rose water, while stirring continuously to avoid clumps.

Let it hydrate for 30–45 minutes until it swells and forms a translucent base.

Step 3: pH Adjustment & Gel Formation

Add Triethanolamine (0.2g) drop by drop to the Carbopol dispersion while stirring.

This will neutralize the Carbopol and form a smooth gel.

Stop once pH reaches around 5.5–6.5 (check with pH paper).

➤ Phase B: Incorporation of Moisturizers & Soothing Agents

Step 4: Add Aloe Vera

Mix in Aloe vera gel (5.0g) and stir until uniform.

Step 5: Add Glycerin and Honey

Add Glycerin (3.0g) and Honey (as per batch) into the gel and mix until fully blended.

➤ Phase C: Active Herbal Powders

Step 6: Add Scrub Powders

Gradually add Pomegranate peel powder, Neem powder, and Turmeric powder.

Mix thoroughly to ensure even distribution and avoid clumping.

Final Steps

Step 7: Mixing

Stir the final mixture gently but thoroughly to ensure all ingredients are well blended.

Step 8: pH Check & Adjustment

Test final pH again; if necessary, adjust slightly with TEA

Step 9: Packaging

Transfer the scrub into sterile, airtight containers.

Label the containers.

Step 10: Storage

Store at room temperature or cool place, away from sunlight. [34]

Process of the preparation of scrub

Evaluation of Face Scrub:

The prepared gel was evaluated for organoleptic properties, pH, irritability, washability, grittiness, foamability, spreadability. [35,36,37]

A Organoleptic Properties

Colour: Visual inspection revealed that the face scrub was light brown in colour.

Odour: The smell of formulation was checked by application of preparation on hand and feels the fragrance of perfume.

Consistency: The consistency of face scrub was found to be semi-solid and smooth by visual examination.

Homogeneity and Texture: A tiny amount of the prepared scrub was tested by pressing it between the thumb and index finger

B. pH

pH of the produced gel was assessed using pH paper. Scrub is lightly applied on pH paper. The pH was discovered to be between 5.5-6.5

Fig 9. pH test

C. Irritability

A small amount of the preparation was applied to the dorsal area of the hand, left on for a short time, and was discovered to be non-irritating. There is no redness occurs.

D. Washability

This test was carried out directly on the skin. After applying the preparation and rinsing the skin with ordinary water, the skin was found to be clear and clean. Finally, washability was evaluated by applying the exfoliant on the skin and rinsing it off with water.

E. Grittiness

Few gritty particles were found in the face scrub. Grittiness testing aims to detect any abrasive particles present in the exfoliant.

F. Foamability

In a graduated measuring cylinder, a small amount of scrub was agitated with water to quantify the foam. To assess foamability, a portion of the

exfoliant was applied to the skin followed by a minimal water addition to observe foam formation.

G. Spreadability

The gel that comes out of the tube behaves in a way that is greatly influenced by its spreadability. It is used to determine the extent of the gel's spreadability on the skin. A glass slide with 100 g of Weight was placed on it above a small amount of sample that had been deposited on the slide. A Small quantity of sample was placed on a glass slide and another slide was placed above them; 100 G of weight was placed on the slide. The amount of time it took the gel to spread out on the slide was measured and determined to be 3 cm in 40 seconds. It was calculated by using following

Formula:

$$S = m \times l / t$$

Whereas,

S = Spreadability

M = Weight placed on slide

L = Length of glass

T = Time taken in seconds

Fig. 10 Spreadability test

RESULT AND DISCUSSION:

Table No.2: Organoleptic evaluation

Sr. No	Parameters	F1	F2	F3
1	Appearance	Semi-solid	Semi-solid	Semi-solid
2	Colour	Yellowish Brown	Mustard yellow	Mustard yellow
3	Odour	Characteristic	Characteristic	Characteristic
4	Consistency	Smooth	Smooth	Smooth
5	Homogeneity	No aggregation	No aggregation	No aggregation

TableNo.3: Physicochemical evaluation

Sr. No	Parameters	F1	F2	F3
1	pH	5.8	5.5	6
2	Grittiness	Small gritty particles	Small gritty particles	Small gritty particles
3	Washability	Easily washable	Washable	Washable
4	Irritability	No irritation	No irritation	No irritation
5	Spreadability	5.30	5.20	5.10
6	Foamability	No	No	No

DISCUSSION

Herbal face scrubs are known to enhance blood circulation, revitalize facial muscles, support skin elasticity, cleanse clogged pores, and exfoliate the skin. The formulated herbal scrub was assessed based on various parameters. Its organoleptic characteristics—including color, smell, consistency, texture, and homogeneity—were examined visually. The scrub exhibited a peanut brown color with no unpleasant odour. The

consistency was found to be appropriate for skin application. The texture and uniformity were evaluated by feeling the formulation on the skin, and the presence of fine particles gave it a slightly gritty and greasy feel, which was considered satisfactory. It demonstrated good washability, being easily rinsed off with plain water. The pH level was measured at 6.5, indicating suitability for skin use. Spreadability was tested using glass plates and was found to be smooth and consistent. No signs of skin irritation, redness, swelling, or

any adverse dermatological reactions were observed.

CONCLUSION

In this study, we developed a herbal scrub gel and evaluated its effectiveness based on several key parameters. The results indicated that the formulation is safe for topical application and helps improve skin health and radiance without causing adverse effects. The incorporation of pomegranate as a natural exfoliant enhanced the scrub's overall performance. Regular use of the scrub may support improved blood circulation and oxygenation of the skin, leaving it feeling smoother, cleaner, and more refreshed. Our primary goal was to formulate a natural facial scrub using plant-based medicinal ingredients to ensure both stability and efficacy. The resulting product contains exfoliating agents that help cleanse the skin, eliminate impurities, and promote an instant glow. Additionally, the active compounds in the herbal scrub possess antibacterial and antimicrobial properties. Unlike formulations containing parabens or sulfates—which may not be suitable for all skin types—our herbal scrub offers a gentler, more skin-friendly alternative. Compared to synthetic options, it demonstrates greater benefits with minimal side effects when prepared using natural components. It is suitable for people of all ages, causes less irritation, and provides visible improvements in skin appearance. Based on our findings, we conclude that this herbal face scrub is a promising natural skincare solution that effectively exfoliates and revitalizes the skin.

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